

STUDIES ON THE DEPENDANCE OF OPTICAL ROTATORY POWER ON
CHEMICAL CONSTITUTION. PART XXXVI. THE ROTATORY
DISPERSION OF PHENYL-, *o*-, *m*- & *p*-TOLYL-IMINO-
AND -AMINOCAMPHOR

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The rotatory dispersion of phenyl-, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-tolylimino and amino-*d*-camphors in different solvents has been found to obey Drude's one-term formula, $[\alpha] = \frac{k_0}{\lambda^2 - \lambda_0^2}$. It is therefore "simple".

The effect of solvents and of the position isomerism of the substituent groups in the benzene ring on the rotatory power of these compounds has been discussed.

The effect of conjugated double bonds on the rotatory power, which is phenomenal in these series of compounds, as well as on the "characteristic" absorption band (λ_0) is also discussed.

In parts I and II of this series of investigations (Singh *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 566; 1920, 117, 980) the rotatory power of phenyl-, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-tolyl-imino- and -amino-*d*-camphor was recorded in two solvents for one wave-length (Na_0). In the present case we have determined the rotatory dispersion of aryliminocamphor derivatives for 6 wave-lengths (λ_{6708} to λ_{5461}) in 6 solvents and in the case of the corresponding aminocamphor derivatives for 12 wave-lengths in the visible region of the spectrum (λ_{6708} to λ_{4358}) in two solvents.

• E X P E R I M E N T A L

Phenyl-, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-tolyl-imino- and -amino-*d*-camphors were prepared by the method of Singh and collaborators (*loc. cit.*).

The rotatory power determinations were made in a 2-dcm. jacketed tube at 25°. The values of λ_0 's, calculated from the dispersion formulae, are given in Tables I to VIII and are expressed as μ or 10^{-4} cm.

Nature of the Rotatory Dispersion

These compounds exhibit "simple" rotatory dispersion as their rotatory power can be expressed by Drude's one-term equation,

$$[\alpha] = \frac{k_0}{\lambda^2 - \lambda_0^2}.$$

It is found that the differences between the observed and the calculated values of the rotatory power, as given in Tables I to VIII, lie within the limits of experimental errors allowed in such measurements. Out of 216 observations, in 170 cases the difference in the observed angle of rotation is within 0.02°, in 24 cases within 0.03° and in the remaining 22 cases, within 0.05°.

TABLE I
Phenylimino-d-camphor.

Line.	Solvent: Benzene		Chloroform		Pyridine		Acetone		Ethyl alcohol		Methyl alcohol				
	Conc. (g./100 c.c.)	$[\alpha]_D^{20}$	obs.	cal.	obs.	cal.	obs.	cal.	obs.	cal.	obs.	cal.			
	0.6880	123.8													
		$\lambda^2=0.1649$													
	λ_0	0.4061													
			obs.	cal.	obs.	cal.	obs.	cal.	obs.	cal.	obs.	cal.			
			(o)	(c)	(o)	(c)	(o)	(c)	(o)	(c)	(o)	(c)			
L ₁₄₇₀₀	433.9°	434.2°	-0.3°	433.5°	434.4°	-0.9°	461.3°	457.4°	+3.9°	400.0°	400.3°	-0.31°	422.5°	422.4°	+0.1°
C ₆₄₈₅	492.0	496.0	-4.0	490.5	492.0	-1.5	519.2	517.6	+1.6	450.0	454.4	-4.4	477.5	478.3	-0.8
L ₁₄₁₀₄	594.6	596.2	-1.6	584.0	583.7	+0.3	612.7	613.1	-0.4	540.8	541.1	-0.3	566.6	566.9	-0.3
N ₆₃₉₃	—	—	—	658.5	657.7	+0.8	688.2	689.8	-1.6	611.7	611.2	+0.5	640.7	638.3	+2.4
H ₆₇₈₀	734.8	731.6	+3.2	702.5	703.7	-1.2	736.0	737.4	-1.4	654.2	655.1	+0.9	684.1	682.6	+1.5
H ₆₅₄₁	927.2	928.5	-1.3	871.5	870.8	+0.7	910.3	910.1	+0.2	815.8	815.8	± 0.0	843.3	843.7	-0.4

TABLE II

Line.	Solvent: Benzene		Chloroform		Pyridine		Acetone		Ethyl alcohol		Methyl alcohol				
	nc. (g./100 c.c.)	$[\alpha]_D^{20}$	obs.	cal.	obs.	cal.	obs.	cal.	obs.	cal.	obs.	cal.			
	0.6500	110.0													
		$\lambda^2=0.1592$													
	λ_0	0.3990													
			obs.	cal.	obs.	cal.	obs.	cal.	obs.	cal.	obs.	cal.			
			(o)	(c)	(o)	(c)	(o)	(c)	(o)	(c)	(o)	(c)			
L ₁₄₇₀₀	378.3°	378.3°	$\pm 0.0°$	329.1°	328.0°	+1.1°	391.0°	388.8°	+2.2°	319.6°	317.6°	-2.0°	288.9°	287.8°	+1.1°
C ₆₄₈₅	433.1	430.9	+2.2	373.5	371.1	+2.4	442.5	440.7	+1.8	—	—	—	326.3	326.2	+0.1
L ₁₄₁₀₄	514.5	515.7	-1.2	440.9	439.5	+1.4	523.1	523.2	-0.1	429.6	427.1	+2.5	387.2	387.2	± 0.0
N ₆₃₉₃	585.5	585.1	+0.4	493.5	494.3	+0.8	588.8	589.8	-1.0	481.0	481.0	± 0.0	435.9	436.3	-0.4
H ₆₇₈₀	631.4°	629.0	+2.4	526.4	528.4	-2.0	—	—	—	515.8	515.0	+0.8	468.4	467.0	+1.4
H ₆₅₄₁	789.6	791.4	-1.8	650.6	651.9	-1.3	783.2	782.5	+0.7	637.5	637.7	-0.2	578.0	578.5	-0.5

TABLE III

m-Tolylimino-d-camphor.

Line.	Solvent: Benzene		Chloroform		Pyridine		Acetone		Ethyl alcohol		Methyl alcohol											
	Conc. (g./100 c.c.)	$[\alpha]$	Calc.	obs.	cal.	o-c.	obs.	cal.	o-c.	obs.	cal.	o-c.										
	0.4120	143.1	$\lambda^3 - 0.1545$	485.5°	484.3°	+1.2°	439.2°	440.6°	-1.4°	481.9°	481.0°	+0.4°	417.5°	417.4°	+0.1°	392.0°	394.2°	-2.2°				
			$\lambda^3 - 0.1590$	548.6°	550.3°	-1.7°	500.0°	501.8°	-1.8°	544.6°	546.6°	-2.0°	472.6°	473.6°	-1.0°	449.0°	449.3°	-0.3°	452.6°	449.3°	-3.3°	
			$\lambda^3 - 0.1570$	654.2°	656.3°	-2.1°	600.0°	600.5°	-0.5°	651.0°	651.3°	-0.3°	561.9°	563.3°	-1.4°	536.0°	537.3°	-1.3°	539.0°	538.7°	+0.3°	
			$\lambda^3 - 0.1613$	742.9°	742.5°	+0.4°	681.7°	681.3°	+0.4°	737.5°	736.2°	+1.3°	637.7°	635.0°	+2.7°	600.0°	608.7°	+8.7°	612.8°	611.9°	-0.9°	
			$\lambda^3 - 0.1570$	798.6°	796.6°	+2.0°	732.5°	732.1°	+0.4°	792.1°	790.8°	+2.3°	683.4°	681.6°	+1.8°	655.0°	653.6°	+1.4°	656.0°	658.3°	-2.3°	
			$\lambda^3 - 0.1613$	994.0°	993.6°	+0.4°	920.8°	920.8°	±0.0°	987.7°	985.4°	+2.3°	847.4°	847.8°	-0.4°	820.5°	820.0°	+0.5°	830.7°	830.8°	-0.1°	
			$\lambda^3 - 0.1570$				1143.0°	1141.0°	+2.0°													
			$\lambda^3 - 0.1613$																			

TABLE IV

p-Tolylimino-d-camphor.

Line.	Solvent: Benzene		Chloroform		Pyridine		Acetone		Ethyl alcohol		Methyl alcohol										
	Conc. (g./100 c.c.)	$[\alpha]$	Calc.	obs.	cal.	o-c.	obs.	cal.	o-c.	obs.	cal.	o-c.									
	0.5000	137.3	$\lambda^3 - 0.1803$	509.0°	509.1°	-0.1°	563.0°	565.3°	-2.3°	535.0°	535.1°	+0.9°	537.0°	535.6°	+1.4°	520.0°	501.0°	+1.0°	508.0°	507.6°	+0.4°
			$\lambda^3 - 0.1803$	585.5°	586.2°	-0.7°	—	—	—	610.0°	613.0°	-3.0°	610.0°	607.3°	+2.7°	560.0°	569.8°	-9.8°	580.0°	580.6°	-0.6°
			$\lambda^3 - 0.1803$	—	—	—	795.0°	795.0°	±0.0°	740.0°	740.4°	-0.4°	720.0°	721.8°	-1.8°	680.0°	680.1°	-0.1°	700.0°	699.7°	+0.3°
			$\lambda^3 - 0.1803$	823.0°	822.8°	+0.2°	902.0°	900.5°	+1.5°	845.0°	846.5°	-1.5°	814.0°	813.1°	+0.9°	770.0°	770.2°	-0.2°	797.0°	798.2°	-1.2°
			$\lambda^3 - 0.1803$	890.0°	892.8°	-2.8°	958.0°	956.7°	+1.3°	—	—	—	872.0°	872.2°	-0.2°	827.5°	826.6°	+0.9°	861.0°	861.2°	-0.2°
			$\lambda^3 - 0.1803$	1166.0°	1165.0°	+1.0°	1212.0°	1212.0°	±0.0°	1172.0°	1171.0°	+1.0°	1030.0°	1028.0°	+2.0°	1037.0°	1036.0°	+1.0°	1008.0°	1008.0°	±0.0°

TABLE V

Phenylamino-d-camphor.

Line	Solvent			Ethyl alcohol		
	Benzene			Ethyl alcohol		
	Conc. (g./100 c.c.)			1.0000		
	Calc. $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} [\alpha] \frac{18.78}{\lambda^2 - 0.1287} \\ \lambda_0 \quad 0.3588 \end{array} \right.$			Calc. $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{29.78}{\lambda^2 - 0.07551} \\ 0.2748 \end{array} \right.$		
	obs.	cal.	<i>o-c.</i>	obs.	cal.	<i>o-c.</i>
	(<i>o</i>)	(<i>c</i>)		(<i>o</i>)	(<i>c</i>)	
Li ₆₇₀₈	59.00°	58.43°	+0.57°	79.5°	79.5°	±0.0°
Cd ₆₄₃₈	—	—	—	86.0	87.8	-1.8
Li ₆₁₀₄	78.00	77.02	+0.98	100.0	100.2	-0.2
Na ₅₁₉₃	84.00	85.92	-1.92	109.0	109.6	-0.6
Hg ₆₇₈₀	90.00	91.41	-1.41	114.5	115.2	-0.7
Hg ₅₄₆₁	112.0	110.7	+1.3	131.0	133.8	-2.8
Ag ₅₂₀₉	133.0	131.7	+1.3	151.0	152.2	-1.2
Cd ₅₀₈₆	143.0	144.4	-1.4	161.0	162.6	-1.6
Cd ₄₈₀₀	186.0	184.7	+1.3	193.0	192.3	+0.7
Cd ₄₆₇₈	—	—	—	209.0	207.7	+1.3
Li ₄₆₀₁	—	—	—	220.0	218.5	+1.5
Hg ₄₃₆₈	—	—	—	260.0	260.0	±0.0

TABLE VI

o-Tolylamino-d-camphor.

Line.	Solvent			Ethyl alcohol		
	Benzene			Ethyl alcohol		
	Conc. (g./100 c.c.)			1.0000		
	Calc. $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} [\alpha] \frac{14.32}{\lambda^2 - 0.1191} \\ \lambda_0 \quad 0.3451 \end{array} \right.$			Calc. $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{25.4}{\lambda^2 - 0.0416} \\ 0.2040 \end{array} \right.$		
	obs.	cal.	<i>o-c.</i>	obs.	cal.	<i>o-c.</i>
	(<i>o</i>)	(<i>c</i>)		(<i>o</i>)	(<i>c</i>)	
Li ₆₇₀₈	43.5°	43.27°	+0.23°	61.0°	62.19°	-1.19°
Cd ₆₄₃₈	49.5	48.88	+0.62	68.0	68.1	-0.1
Li ₆₁₀₄	56.5	56.53	-0.03	75.0	76.76	-1.76
Na ₅₈₉₁	62.5	62.77	-0.27	82.5	83.1	-0.6
Hg ₆₇₈₀	66.5	66.61	-0.11	87.0	86.84	+0.16
Hg ₅₄₆₁	80.0	79.91	+0.09	99.0	99.0	±0.0
Ag ₅₂₀₉	93.0	94.08	-1.08	111.5	110.6	+0.9
Cd ₅₀₈₆	100.0	102.7	-2.7	117.0	116.9	+0.1
Cd ₄₈₀₀	—	—	—	135.0	134.5	+0.5
Cd ₄₆₇₈	143.0	143.5	-0.5	—	—	—
Li ₄₆₀₁	154.0	154.5	-0.5	151.0	148.2	+2.8

TABLE VII

m-Tolylamino-d-camphor.

Solvent	Benzene			Ethyl alcohol		
	1.0000			1.0000		
Conc. (g./100 c.c.)	Calc. $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} [\alpha] \frac{28.54}{\lambda^2 - 0.0623} \\ \lambda_0 \quad 0.2496 \end{array} \right.$			Calc. $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{28.89}{\lambda^2 - 0.0447} \\ 0.2114 \end{array} \right.$		
Line.	obs.	cal.	<i>o-c</i>	obs.	cal.	<i>o-c</i>
	(o)	(c)		(o)	(c)	
Li ₆₇₀₀	74.0°	73.60°	+0.40°	70.50°	71.29°	-0.79°
Cd ₆₄₃₈	83.0	81.04	+1.96	78.50	78.12	+0.38
Li ₆₁₀₄	92.0	91.98	+0.02	86.0	88.12	-2.12
Na ₅₈₉₃	102.0	100.2	+1.80	95.0	95.52	-0.52
Hg ₆₇₈₀	107.0	105.0	+2.00	100.0	99.84	+0.16
Hg ₆₄₆₁	121.0	121.0	±0.00	114.5	114.0	+0.50
Ag ₅₇₀₉	140.0	136.6	+3.40	127.5	127.5	±0.0
Cd ₅₀₈₆	148.0	145.3	+2.70	134.0	135.0	-1.0
Cd ₄₉₀₈	167.0	169.7	-2.70	155.0	155.6	-0.6
Li ₄₆₀₃	191.0	190.9	+0.1	—	—	—
Hg ₄₃₅₈	—	—	—	200.0	198.8	+1.2

TABLE VIII

-Tolylamino-d-camphor.

Solvent	Benzene			Ethyl alcohol		
	1.0000			1.0000		
Conc. (g./100 c.c.)	Calc. $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} [\alpha] \frac{21.61}{\lambda^2 - 0.0990} \\ \lambda_0 \quad 0.3146 \end{array} \right.$			Calc. $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{24.82}{\lambda^2 - 0.0584} \\ 0.2417 \end{array} \right.$		
Line.	obs.	cal.	<i>o-c</i>	obs.	cal.	<i>o-c</i>
	(o)	(c)		(o)	(c)	
Li ₆₇₀₃	67.00°	67.58°	-0.58°	67.50°	63.39°	-1.89°
Cd ₆₄₃₈	70.50	68.50	+2.00	70.00	69.72	+0.28
Li ₆₁₀₄	79.00	79.02	-0.02	79.00	79.05	-0.05
Na ₅₈₉₃	88.00	87.06	+0.94	84.50	85.96	-1.46
Hg ₆₇₈₀	93.00	91.91	+1.09	90.00	90.05	-0.05
Hg ₆₄₆₁	108.5	108.5	±0.00	103.5	103.5	±0.00
Ag ₅₇₀₉	126.0	125.4	+0.60	120.0	116.6	+3.4
Cd ₅₀₈₆	—	—	—	123.5	124.0	-0.50
Li ₄₆₀₇	190.0	191.6	-1.60	162.0	161.8	+0.20
Hg ₄₃₅₈	235.0	237.5	-2.5	189.5	188.7	+0.80

The Effect of Solvent on Rotatory Power

The molecular rotatory power, $[M]_{D}^{25}$, of these compounds in different solvents is given in Table IX. The values of molecular rotation constants, K_{ϵ} s, are also given in parenthesis. The order of decreasing rotatory power is as follows:

1. *Phenylimino-d-camphor*: benzene > pyridine > chloroform > ethyl alcohol > acetone > methyl alcohol. The sequence is in the reverse order of their dielectric constants except for pyridine and acetone.

2. *o-Tolylimino-d-camphor*: benzene > pyridine > chloroform > acetone > ethyl alcohol > methyl alcohol. The sequence is in the reverse order of their dielectric constants except for pyridine.

3. *m-Tolylimino-d-camphor*: benzene > pyridine > chloroform > acetone > methyl alcohol > ethyl alcohol. The sequence agrees in the reverse order of their dielectric constants except for pyridine and methyl alcohol.

TABLE IX

 $[M]_{D}^{25}$

No.	Substance. (Formula)	Benzene. § [2.28]	CHCl ₃ . [5.2]	Pyridine. [12.5]	Acetone. [21.6]	EtOH. [25.8]	MeOH. [31.2]
1.	R* = N	2235* (298.4)‡	2100* (317.1)	2194* (336.4)	1966* (287.5)	2032* (309.4)	1930* (297.4)
2.	R = N-	2013 (280.5)	1659 (255.5)	1997 (299.0)	1625 (244.8)	1473 (221.8)	1399 (184.7)
3.	R = N-	2534 (364.9)	2348 (326.9)	2519 (363.7)	2161 (318.2)	2092 (295.2)	2118 (290.2)
4.	R = N-	2973 (350.1)	3090 (438.3)	2988 (381.2)	2754 (410.1)	2644 (375.8)	2800 (365.4)
5.	RH.NH-	272.1 (45.62)	—	—	—	318.4 (71.78)	—
6.	RH.NH-	205.6 (36.80)	—	—	—	254.4 (65.27)	—
7.	RH.NH-	311.0 (73.33)	—	—	—	294.3 (74.25)	—
8.	RH.NH-	278.8 (55.54)	—	—	—	266.0 (63.80)	—

§. The values in square brackets under the solvents refer to dielectric constants.

‡. The values in brackets refer to molecular rotation constants.

*. R stands for C₉H₁₄

4. *p*-Tolylimino-*d*-camphor : chloroform > pyridine > benzene > methyl alcohol > acetone > ethyl alcohol. The sequence agrees in the reverse order of their dielectric constants except for benzene and methyl alcohol.

In the case of phenyl- and *o*-tolyl-amino-*d*-camphor, the rotatory power, like the dielectric constants, is higher in ethyl alcohol than in benzene, whereas in the case of *m* and *p*-tolylaminocamphors the rotatory power is in the reverse order of their dielectric constants.

The Effect of Position Isomerism of the Substituent Group in the Benzene Ring on the Rotatory Power

In Table XA, the increasing order of the molecular rotatory power, $[M]_{5461}^{26}$, of phenyl-, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-tolyliminocamphors is given. The order of K_{θ} 's, the molecular rotation constants, is also given in square brackets.

TABLE X A

Solvent.	$[M]_{5461}^{26}$	Solvent.	$[M]_{5461}^{26}$
Benzene	$o < un < m < p$ [$o < un < p < m$]	Acetone	$o < un < m < p$ [$o < un < m < p$]
Chloroform	$o < un < m < p$ [$o < un < m < p$]	Ethyl alcohol	$o < un < m < p$ [$o < m < un < p$]
Pyridine	$o < un < m < p$ [$o < un < m < p$]	Methyl alcohol	$o < un < m < p$ [$o < m < un < p$]

In all the six solvents the increasing order of the molecular rotatory power of these aryliminocamphor derivatives is the same, namely : $o < un < m < p$.

The results are in conformity with Frankland's "lever arm" hypothesis (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1896, 69, 1583) as well as its electrostatic modification by Rule (*ibid.*, 1924, 125, 1121). Comparison of the values of K_{θ} 's, however, shows that the order of increasing rotation constants agrees with "lever arm" hypothesis of Frankland or its electrostatic modification of Rule only in chloroform, pyridine and acetone.

In no case is Cohen's rule (*ibid.*, 1911, 99, 1058), namely, the rotatory power of the *o*-derivative differs more from that of the unsubstituted compound than does that of the *m*- or *p*- derivative, obeyed in these compounds (Table IX).

In Table XB, the order of increasing molecular rotatory power of phenyl-, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-tolylaminocamphor derivatives is given. The order of K_{θ} 's, is also given in brackets.

TABLE X B

Solvents.	$[M]_{5461}^{35}$
Benzene	$o < un < p < m$ [$o < un < p < m$]
Ethyl alcohol	$o < p < m < un$ [$p < o < un < m$]

In no case is the generalisation of Frankland or of Rule obeyed.

Cohen's rule, however, is strictly followed in the case of two solvents investigated, namely, benzene and ethyl alcohol (Table IX).

The Effect of Unsaturation on Rotatory Power

The molecular powers, $[M]_{5461}^{85^\circ}$, of the arylimino- and -amino-camphor derivatives in benzene and ethyl alcohol are given in Table XI. The differences in the values of the rotatory power of the aryliminocamphor compounds and their corresponding amino derivatives are also shown in the table. The remarkable fall in the rotatory power of aryliminocamphor derivatives on their reduction into the corresponding amino compounds may be correlated with a break (dotted line, Ib) in the conjugation of the double bonds of the carbonyl, azethenoid and the phenyl groups present in the aryliminocamphor derivatives thus :

TABLE XI

Substance.	Benzene		Ethyl alcohol	
	$[M]_{5461}^{85^\circ}$	Fall in rotation.	$[M]_{5461}^{85^\circ}$	Fall in rotation.
I. (a) $R=N-$	2235°		2032°	
(b) $RH.NH-$		1962.9°		1713.6°
II. (a) $R=N-$	2013°		1473°	
(b) $RH.NH-$		1807.4°		1218.6°
III. (a) $R=N-$	2534°		2092°	
(b) $RH.NH-$		2223.0°		1797.7°
IV. (a) $R=N-$	2973°		2644°	
(b) $RH.NH-$		2694.2°		2378.0°
			266.0°	

The Influence of Solvent, the Nature and Position of the Substituent group in the Benzene ring and of the Unsaturated Conjugated double bonds present in Optically active compounds on the Wave-length of the "characteristic" Absorption band in the Ultraviolet region.

TABLE XII
Characteristic wave-lengths (λ_0 s) in Å.

Substance (formula)	Benzene.	CHCl ₃ .	Pyridine.	Acetone.	EtOH.	MeOH.
1. R=N—	4061	3835	3806	3899	3821	3798
2. R=N—	3990	3802	3851	3842	3845	4081
3. R=N—	3930	3987	3918	3886	3962	4014
4. R=N—	4246	3954	4130	3869	3947	4096
5. RH.NH=	3588	—	—	—	2748	—
6. RH.NH=	3451	—	—	—	2040	—
7. RH.NH—	2496	—	—	—	2114	—
8. RH.NH—	3246	—	—	—	2417	—

R stands for C_7H_{14}

In Table XII are given the wave-lengths of the "characteristic" absorption bands deduced from the one-term Drude's equation, $[\alpha] = \frac{k_0}{\lambda^2 - \lambda_0^2}$, in eight optically active compounds, namely, phenyl-, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-tolyl-imino- and -amino-*d*-camphors. The "characteristic" absorption band of phenylimino-*d*-camphor in solvents such as chloroform, pyridine, methyl alcohol and ethyl alcohol is shifted with minor variations to the red end of the spectrum when a hydrogen atom of the benzene ring is replaced by a

methyl group in the *ortho*, *meta* or *para* position, whereas, in benzene and acetone solutions the shift is towards the ultraviolet end.

The wave-lengths of the "characteristic" absorption bands of phenylamino-*d*-camphor ($\lambda_0 = 3588\text{\AA}$ in benzene solution and $\lambda_0 = 2748\text{\AA}$ in ethyl alcohol solution) are shifted to the ultraviolet end of the spectrum when a hydrogen atom in the benzene nucleus is substituted by a methyl group. It is, however, significant that both the solvents, namely, benzene and ethyl alcohol act in the same way, whereas, in the case of the corresponding tolylimino derivatives they generally act in the opposite sense as regards their influence on the shift of the "characteristic" absorption band.

It has been remarked above that the breaking of the conjugation between the double bonds of carbonyl group, azethenoid group and the benzene ring produces a phenomenal fall in the rotatory power in the resulting amino derivatives. Similarly the "characteristic" absorption band has been very considerably shifted from the near ultraviolet end of the spectrum to the far distant ultraviolet e.g., from 3962 to 2114 $\text{\AA}$ in ethyl alcohol and from 3930 to 2496 $\text{\AA}$ in benzene in the case of *meta* derivatives (vide Table XII).

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